

Kinetics and mechanism of iridium(III) catalyzed oxidation of some cyclic alcohols by potassium bromate in acidic medium

Sheila Srivastava*, Rajendra Kumar Sharma and Sarika Singh

Chemical Laboratories, Feroze Gandhi College, Rae Bareilly-229 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : she_ila72@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Kinetic study of iridium(III) catalyzed oxidation of cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol by potassium bromate in acidic solution have been made in the presence of mercuric acetate. The reaction exhibits first order with respect to oxidant, zero-order with respect to substrates. Rate is not affected by hydrogen ion concentration, however Cl^- enhances the rate. A plausible mechanism based on these observations has been suggested.

Keywords : Iridium(III) catalysis, cyclic alcohols, potassium bromate, kinetics and mechanism.

Metal in catalyzed oxidation of organic compounds has been extensively investigated by workers worldwide¹. In the present investigation Ir^{III} catalyzed oxidation of some cyclic alcohols (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol) by acidic solution of potassium bromate has been reported.

Experimental

Material :

Iridium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) solution (1 L) was prepared by dissolving 1 g sample in HCl ($0.018 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). Aqueous solution of cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol (E. Merck), sodium perchlorate, mercuric acetate (E. Merck), potassium bromate (B.D.H.) etc. were prepared by dissolving the weighed samples in double distilled water. Perchloric acid (E. Merck, 60%) was prepared directly by dissolving appropriate volume of sample in double distilled water.

Deuterium oxide (D_2O) purity (99.4%) was supplied by B.A.R.C., Mumbai. 1% starch solution was prepared afresh each day before titration. Black coated reaction vessels were used to exclude photochemical effects.

Requisite volumes of desired concentrations of all reagents were taken in a reaction vessel which were suspended in a water bath maintained at $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A measured volume of potassium bromate solution also maintained separately at same temperature was rapidly poured into reaction vessel. Process of reaction was followed by assaying aliquots of the reaction mixture for

unconsumed bromate iodometrically using starch as indicator after suitable time intervals.

Results and discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was ascertained by equilibrating the reaction mixture containing excess of potassium bromate over cyclic alcohols separately (in varying ratios) at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (323 K) for 48 h (Table 1). Estimation of residual bromate in different reactions showed that one mole of cyclic alcohol consumes two moles of bromate.

The following stoichiometric equation could be formulated :

($n = 1, 2$ and 3 for cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol respectively)

The end products obtained (corresponding ketones) were identified by TLC and also through dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) derivative as follows.

1 ml of the reaction mixture in dilute HCl was added to 3 ml of the 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine solution in

Table 1. Stoichiometric results for oxidation of cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol

$10^3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 [\text{Substrate}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]^* \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3} (\text{residual})$			$[\text{BrO}_3^-]^c / [\text{Substrate}]$		
		Cyclopent.	Cyclohex.	Cyclohept.	Cyclopent.	Cyclohex.	Cyclohept.
12.50	1.00	10.60	10.42	10.56	1.90	2.08	1.94
10.00	1.00	8.02	7.94	8.10	1.98	2.06	1.90
5.00	1.00	2.90	3.06	2.92	2.10	1.94	2.08
2.50	1.00	0.48	0.44	0.52	2.02	2.06	1.98
12.50	2.00	8.62	8.44	8.50	1.94	2.03	2.00
12.50	3.00	6.38	6.45	6.43	2.04	2.02	2.02
12.50	4.00	4.64	4.48	4.56	1.97	2.02	1.99
12.50	5.00	2.70	2.64	2.48	1.96	1.95	2.01

$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol), $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol } \text{dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 323 K, time = 48 h, $[\text{BrO}_3^-]^* = [\text{BrO}_3^-]$ left unconsumed after 48 h, $[\text{BrO}_3^-]^c = [\text{BrO}_3^-] - [\text{BrO}_3^-]^*$ i.e. oxidant consumed during the reaction.

dilute HCl and shaken well. A yellowish precipitate was formed which was the corresponding hydrazone according to following equation

The derivatives were dried and their melting points determined. The DNP derivatives of cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and cycloheptanone recorded melting points 145, 160 and 148 °C (actual melting points being 146,

162 and 148 °C) respectively².

The kinetics of oxidation of cyclic alcohols was investigated at several initial reactant concentrations (Table 2). The first order constants k_1 were calculated from the plots of unconsumed bromate against time. Values of k_1 at all initial concentration of bromate revealed that reaction follows first order with respect to oxidant. Zero-order dependence on cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol was observed. Variation of perchloric acid concentration did not bring about significant changes in rate constant i.e. reaction exhibits zeroth-order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$. The reaction was markedly influenced by increase in concentration of iridium(III) chloride. A plot of $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs $\log [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ (Fig. 1) gives a straight line with slope of 1.05, 1.07 and 1.05 for cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol respectively which confirms first order kinetics with respect to Ir^{III} concentration.

Kinetic results (Table 3) show negligible effect of ionic strength, mercury(II) acetate and positive effect of $[\text{Cl}^-]$. The values of energy of activation (ΔE_a), entropy of activation (ΔS^*), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*), Arrhenius factor (A) and free energy (ΔG^*) were calculated from the measurement of rate at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K (Fig. 2) and these values are recorded in Table 4. The negligible effect of mercury(II) acetate excludes the possibility of its involvement either as catalyst or as an oxidant because it does not help the reaction proceed without bromate. First order dependence on [bromate] suggests that it is involved in rate determining step.

Ir^{III} chloride has a number of possible chloro species

Table 2. Effect of reactant on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2 [\text{S}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
			Cyclopentanol	Cyclohexanol	Cycloheptanol
0.83	5.00	1.00	0.52	0.68	1.02
1.00	5.00	1.00	0.66	0.58	1.20
1.25	5.00	1.00	0.82	1.08	1.52
1.66	5.00	1.00	1.10	1.46	2.06
2.50	5.00	1.00	1.68	2.24	3.14
3.33	5.00	1.00	2.30	2.90	3.98
1.00	0.75	1.00	0.62	0.90	1.20
1.00	1.25	1.00	0.57	0.80	1.34
1.00	1.66	1.00	0.68	0.88	1.16
1.00	2.50	1.00	0.63	0.94	1.40
1.00	10.00	1.00	0.60	0.83	1.28
1.00	20.00	1.00	0.68	0.89	1.06
1.00	25.00	1.00	0.72	0.84	1.30
1.00	5.00	0.83	0.58	0.86	1.10
1.00	5.00	1.25	0.64	0.87	1.24
1.00	5.00	1.66	0.70	0.92	1.28
1.00	5.00	2.50	0.74	0.95	1.15
1.00	5.00	5.00	0.68	0.91	1.30

$[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol), $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cycloheptanol); $2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclohexanol), temp. 308 K.

Table 3. Effect of variation of chloride ion, mercury(II) acetate and ionic strength (μ)

$10^2 [\text{KCl}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{NaHClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
			Cyclopentanol	Cyclohexanol	Cycloheptanol
0.20	1.25	-	0.49	0.64	1.02
0.25	1.25	-	0.54	0.70	1.06
0.50	1.25	-	0.58	0.74	1.13
1.00	1.25	-	0.66	0.79	1.20
2.00	1.25	-	0.71	0.85	1.26
2.50	1.25	-	0.79	0.91	1.30
4.00	1.25	-	0.91	0.99	1.36
1.00	0.83	-	0.67	0.83*	1.28
1.00	1.00	-	0.72	0.93*	1.36
1.00	1.66	-	0.62	0.96*	1.15
1.00	2.50	-	0.68	0.80*	1.40
1.00	5.00	-	0.75	0.86*	1.10
1.00	1.25	1.00	0.75	0.80*	1.30
1.00	1.25	2.00	0.60	0.95*	1.42
1.00	1.25	2.50	0.78	0.75*	1.28
1.00	1.25	5.00	0.62	1.00*	1.36
1.00	1.25	10.00	0.57	1.10*	1.10
1.00	1.25	12.50	0.70	0.90*	1.05

$[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol), $[\text{cyclopentanol}] = [\text{cyclohexanol}] = [\text{cycloheptanol}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 308 K, * $[\text{KCl}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs $\log [Ir^{III}]$ in oxidation of cyclopentanol (A), cyclohexanol (B) and cycloheptanol (C) at 308 K. $[Hg(OAc)_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[KCl] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cycloheptanol); $2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclohexanol), $[HClO_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[KBrO_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclopentanol] = [cyclohexanol] = [cycloheptanol] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs $1/T \times 10^4$ in oxidation of cyclopentanol (A), cyclohexanol (B) and cycloheptanol (C). $[KBrO_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Hg(OAc)_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[KCl] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cycloheptanol); $2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclohexanol), $[cyclopentanol] = [cyclohexanol] = [cycloheptanol] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ir^{III}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol).

in solution. It has been reported that in acidic medium iridium(III) chloride exists³ as $[IrCl_6]^{3-}$. Our experimental data indicate that addition of chloride ion has positive

effect on the reaction velocity and also that conditions for pseudo first order exist.

Table 4. Activation parameters for acid bromate oxidation of cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol

Parameters	Temp. (K)	Cyclopentanol	Cyclohexanol	Cycloheptanol
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	303	0.48	0.61	1.88
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	308	0.66	0.85	1.20
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	313	0.98	1.26	1.64
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	318	1.38	1.75	2.36
ΔE_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	308	58.59	63.42	52.84
ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	308	69.60	69.90	65.80
ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	308	-11.17	-6.57	-13.15
ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	308	73.04	71.92	69.85
$\log A$	-	10.56	11.56	10.13
k_t (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	308	4.92	6.34	7.16

$[KBrO_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Hg(OAc)_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclopentanol] = [cyclohexanol] = [cycloheptanol] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ir^{III}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol), $[KCl] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cycloheptanol); $2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclohexanol).

Since Cl^- ion increases the rate of reaction, $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ should be the reactive species.

The following reaction steps are suggested on the basis of the above discussion for oxidation of cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol by potassium bromate in presence of iridium(III) chloride as a catalyst which follow similar kinetics.

Considering the above reaction steps and applying steady state approximation the rate law may be derived and written in terms of loss of bromate ion i.e.

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1k_2[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{HBrO}_3]}{k_{-1} + k_1[\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (A)$$

The factor 2 is introduced because two molecules of bromate is used per molecule of substrate.

Fig. 3. Plot of $1/(-dc/dt)$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ in oxidation of cyclopentanol (A), cyclohexanol (B) and cycloheptanol (C) at 308 K. $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 13.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol); $16.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (cycloheptanol), $[\text{cyclopentanol}] = [\text{cyclohexanol}] = [\text{cycloheptanol}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

or

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{2Kk_2[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{HBrO}_3]}{1 + K[\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (B)$$

where $K = (k_1/k_{-1})$

The rate law (A) and (B) derived fully accords with the kinetic results which fulfills requirement for a negative dielectric effect and zero effect of ionic strength of the medium requiring interaction between an ion and at least a dipole.

The rate expression obtained in equation (A) can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\text{rate}} = \frac{1}{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]/dt} = \frac{k_{-1}}{2k_2k_1[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{HBrO}_3]} + \frac{k_1[\text{Cl}^-]}{2k_2k_1[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{HBrO}_3]}$$

or

$$\frac{1}{\text{rate}} = \frac{1}{2k_2K[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{HBrO}_3]}$$

Note

$$+ \frac{1}{2k_2[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{HBrO}_3]} \quad (\text{C})$$

A graph plotted between $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ at constant $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$ and $[\text{HBrO}_3]$ would give a line, the value of intercept and slope enable us to calculate k_2 and K values. The values of k_2 obtained from such a plot (Fig. 3) are 3.97, 4.79 and 5.97 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ for cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol, cycloheptanol respectively. The values obtained for K are 7.95×10^2 , 6.34×10^2 and $3.45 \times 10^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$ for cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol, cycloheptanol respectively. The k_2 values for oxidation of cyclic alcohols show that cycloheptanol oxidized faster than cyclohexanol and cyclopentanol i.e. oxidation of

cyclic alcohols are in the following order :

cycloheptanol > cyclohexanol > cyclopentanol

The high values of the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) indicate highly solvated transition state.

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